

On Affect and Mixtapes

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Come discover if your music listening habits say anything about you 🎵 ✨

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Description: This story, from the “Library of Experiences” collection, is based on a playlist and used in the workshop “On Affect and Mixtapes.” It explores how playlists, as curated compilations, can frame and measure user behavior on platforms like Spotify. It prompts critical reflection on how these platforms shape our understanding of data and potentially influence our sense of self. Drawing on Mike Michael's (2014) concept of “anecdotalization” as an “Inventive Method,” (Lury & Wakeford, 2014) the story highlights how anecdotal accounts can illuminate the participant experience within the workshop context, shaping alternative understandings of mediated data relations. Moreover, it serves to recognize the performativity of research in design, acknowledging the active role of storytelling in knowledge production.

I'm a child of the 80s, and making mixtapes was a rite of passage. Do you know of mixtapes? Playlists are the modern equivalent of mixtapes, except instead of playing 30 or 45 minutes on each side, you can put as many songs as your music repertoire holds and some more.

There is an “art” in creating mixtapes, and this “know-how” was brought into creating the playlist: “I'm a Little Kinder, Baby”. In “High Fidelity,” John Cusack's character Rob explains that *“the making of a good compilation tape is a very subtle art. Many do's and don'ts. First of all, you're using someone else's poetry to express how you feel. This is a delicate thing.”*

Unlike mixtapes, Spotify playlists allow for ongoing curation and modification. A mixtape has an immediacy to it, but a Spotify playlist does not.

This playlist began as a wish, a request: boy, you can keep on calling (a reference to song #1, Keep on Calling, Album Small Crimes by Nilüfer Yanya). It was also my version of a mixed tape to convey my feelings to the person who eventually became my partner in crime with whom to commit petty crimes (a reference to song #27 Hell N Back, Album Hell N Back by Baker).

This playlist compiles four years of memories. It tells a story from beginning to end, including all the beautiful messiness in between. It is an ode to love declared through forty songs. In a way, it even foreshadowed my relationship's demise before I could acknowledge its end. The climax of the story, a point near the end of the third act, opens with a letter to my younger self (a reference to song #32, A Letter to My Younger Self, Album: Dreaming Lucid by Ambar Lucid). It reminded me that the universe would give me many flowers and that there was no need for crying. Act 3 ends with the realization that growing wiser through heartache also fosters kindness and the understanding that there are moments when you need to let go (a reference to song #40, Rose in the Dark Album: Rose in the Dark by Cleo Sol).

Songs are a powerful thing, and a playlist is a way of using someone else's poetry to express how you feel. Our feelings are indeed one of the frontiers for behavioral modification.

Predictions can be derived from user-generated data, which includes listening history, song ratings, saved songs, and playlist content. This data can potentially reveal your emotional state. The question arises: would you be comfortable with a company retaining this information about you?

"In 2016, evidence emerged that Spotify had begun filling some of their mood-oriented playlists with fake artists, illustrating the company's interest to use playlists as a device for framing and measuring user behavior" (Turner, 2016 as cited in Eriksson et al., 2019, p. 5).

Thereafter, in 2018, Spotify filed a patent that proposed the capability to "make observations" concerning a user's surroundings and emotions. Currently, "Spotify's interaction design reorganizes music consumption around behaviors, feelings, and moods, which are channeled through curated playlists and motivational messages that change several times a day". In this way, "music has become data, and data has become contextual material for user profiling at scale" (Eriksson et al., 2019, p. 5).

Would you consider profiling emotions and behavior through your listening habits problematic?